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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7996770>**Abstract**

Recent research has focused on the analysis of the causes of visitors' behavioral intentions and how they relate to them. However, domestic travel is typically one of the tourist sectors that academics and decision-makers in developing nations give the least attention to. In order to better understand the relationship between domestic travelers' motivations (push and pull), satisfaction, and behavioral intentions (intention to revisit and willingness to recommend), we looked at both the direct and indirect effects of motivations on behavioral intentions in this study. Create a model of domestic tourism behavior. The Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) approach of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was used to structurally examine this relationship utilizing data from its 15 domestic tourists from his four sites in Bukhara. It was finished. It has been established that overall pleasure was significantly predicted by both push and pull travel motivations. Furthermore, it was discovered that pull travel motivations directly impacted revisit intentions and recommendation intent. On the other hand, overall satisfaction had a greater influence on the intention to return than willingness to make recommendations. The association between travel motivation and return intentions was also in part driven by general contentment. The direct and indirect impacts of push travel motivation were also examined in this study. The findings of this study have significant ramifications for destination managers and researchers who are seeking to enhance domestic tourism and are thinking about how motivational factors affect satisfaction and behavioral intentions.

KEY: *domestic tourism,satisfaction,safe,recommendation,transport,SEM,MLE***Introduction**

Tourism and transport development are two interdependent issues.

Tourists want safe, fast and comfortable transport services that they can pay for from their own budgets. The choice of a particular mode of transport and its various combinations is determined by its characteristics and passenger motivations. They have to choose between four main types of transportation to arrive at the desired destination.

The choice of the form of tourist transport by the tourist or is made taking into account the following parameters:

- * the distance to be travelled from the tourist residence to the holiday destination,
- * the time factor--it is important that the voyage can be carried out at the desired time and that the travel time does not exceed certain acceptable limits for the tourist in the context of the total vacation time,

- * the availability and accessibility of the service--from the very beginning must have the means to carry passengers on the route or destination,
- * safety and regularity--the standards related to these objectives are becoming more and more demanding for all forms of transport,
- * the comfort of the voyage--with reference to all the psychological and physiological sensations felt by tourists inside the vehicle during the voyage.

In the actual development of tourist traffic, a wide range of means of transport are used. The usage of one, or their combined use, are determined by factors related to the specificity of the journey and the particularities of the means of transport, as well as by elements related to the psychology of the tourists. Of these, the travel distance and travel duration, the itineraries characteristics, the state of the communication routes and the traffic intensity, the regularity and security of the trips, the reason for the voyage and the group membership, the comfort of the trip, the level of the tariffs.

Lirerature review

Tourist behavioral intentions (revisiting and recommending) often vary from a destination's perceived desirability (Um et al., 2006) to actual destination attributes (Hsieh, 2012; Ngoc and Trinh, 2015). ; Mat Som).) Rich et al., 2012). In addition, destination image, perceived quality, visitor motivation and satisfaction may predict future tourist behavior (Elgammal and Ghanem, 2016; Ranjanthran and Mohammed, 2010; Lee, 2009).

Moreover, a number of studies demonstrate that satisfaction has a direct positive impact on tourist behavioral intentions in general, and visitor intentions to revisit and recommend in particular. Several previous empirical studies have confirmed the relationship between satisfaction and tourists' behavioral intentions (both proposal intentions and return plans) (Prayag and Ryan, 2012; Žabkar et al., 2010). ; Do Valle et al., 2006). Huang and Hsu (2009), on the other hand, argue that satisfaction only affects Chinese travelers' intentions to revisit Hong Kong. On the other hand, a study by Lee et al. (2007) on Korean Demilitarized Zone tourists found that satisfaction only affected tourists' recommendation intentions. According to Do Valle et al. (2006) satisfaction significantly predicts likelihood of return visits and willingness to recommend others to visit the same international destination.

Many previous studies have confirmed that tourist satisfaction is a successful mediating variable in tourism behavior models (Lee, 2007, 2009; Osman et al., 2006). Satisfaction has been identified as a successful mediator in the relationship between destination image and loyalty (Ramseook-Munhurrun et al., 2015; Prayag and Ryan, 2012). Place attachments and future intentions (Prayag and Ryan, 2012). Tourist attitudes, motivations, destination images, and future behavioral intentions (Lee, 2009). Motivation and service loyalty (Suardana et al., 2014).

Satisfaction is also mentioned in the literature as a perfect mediator of the relationship between pushing and pulling motivations. Tourist behavioral intentions in different settings and situations. A study conducted on foreign tourists found that overall tourist satisfaction was the perfect mediator in the relationship between tourist motivation and destination loyalty (Battour et al. al., 2012). Research results by Khuong and Ha (2014) also support the importance of the mediating effect of goal satisfaction on the relationship between push and pull motivation factors, especially return intentions. The mediating role of satisfaction between motivation and loyalty was also demonstrated in a study of festival-goers (Lee and Hsu, 2013). Similarly, satisfaction acts as a moderator in relation to tourist motivation and

future behavior in natural recreation areas (Lee, 2009). Thus, the literature supports the relationship between motivation, satisfaction, and tourist behavioral intentions in different contexts. However, based on a review of previous studies, the following research gaps were identified. First, despite the fact that domestic tourism makes the highest economic contribution among tourism, almost all research has been conducted on foreign tourists. Second, some studies have used either push or pull motivational factors in relational structural studies, viewing motivation as a single component that is in opposition to traditional push and pull motivations. Adherence can be measured in terms of intent to return and recommend, but previous studies have not considered considering them separately at the configuration level due to conceptual differences. Finally, the relationship between motivation, satisfaction, and tourists' behavioral intentions has never been structurally studied, despite the differences in tourist personalities and socio-psychological structures.

Methodology

Structural equation modeling (SEM) is a powerful multivariate analysis technique that is widely used in the social sciences. Its applications range from analysis of simple relationships between variables to complex analyses of measurement equivalence for first and higher-order constructs. It provides a flexible framework for developing and analyzing complex relationships among multiple variables that allow researchers to test the validity of theory using empirical models. Perhaps its greatest advantage is the ability to manage measurement error, which is one of the greatest limitations of most studies. Although its application has been seen in many disciplines, it has yet to be extensively used in medical research and epidemiology.

The use of SEM has now become widespread across research domains. In psychology, for example, the citation frequency of SEM has steadily increased from 164 in 1994 to 343 in 2000 and then to 742 in the last year (based on the citation frequency of SEM and of PsychINFO database 1970-2010). This suggests that researchers recognize its application to a variety of research questions, types of data, and methods of study. An increase in use of sophisticated tools of analysis reflects the increase in complexity of empirical models and theoretical developments seen in the published research over the years.

The development of tourism transport is conditioned by the existence of suitable means of transportation.

Roads, expressways, railway lines, stations, bus stops, rivers, harbors, airports, etc. Today, the modernization and diversification of means of transportation have led to significant development in the tourism industry. Advances in this area have facilitated the inclusion of resources located far from tourist centers and those that have overcome some natural barriers into the tourism sector.

The main share in the overall structure of transport services belongs to air transport. The largest number of tourists, especially those traveling long distances, uses aviation services. At the same time, the aircraft can, figuratively speaking, be called the transport of individuals. The most massive flows of tourists traveling for resort, business, entertainment, and educational purposes are individual tourists. And it is they who most often use air transport.

Road transport can rightfully be called a transport of general use, since it is used everywhere: from transfers and excursions, intra-route transportation by buses to the rental of small cars by tourists for personal use on vacation. Buses and cars transport of local and intra-regional importance. Bus sightseeing tours with visits to several cities and places of interest are

especially popular. It is convenient for tourists that they can travel along the route and within the city on their own transport.

Tourists nowadays prefer car rentals to explore new places, as they have the flexibility to plan their own itinerary without fear of relying on public transport. Car rental services allow customers to travel to locations of their choice according to their needs. In addition, due to the increase in disposable income, more and more people are taking short trips. Customers prefer to rent a car instead of using their own vehicle. Airport rentals are the most common as tourists either rent a car as soon as they arrive in a new country and either keep the car with them for the duration of their stay or drop them off at a convenient drop off point. Its history dates back to his twentieth century, where two important figures an promoted this business in the United States. After nearly 100 years of development, the annual turnover of car rental business has reached his US\$100 billion, playing an important role in the world's economic development. For example, about one-third of new cars are sold through rental each year in the United States.

Similarly, in Japan, his 2 million units, which account for 15 percent of new cars, are sold in the same way. Transportation services play an important role in tourism that requires some movement to or from a place. Car rental companies play an important role in facilitating travel by providing services that allow tourists to easily navigate within their destination.

As the importance of travel facilities, especially car rentals, seems to gain more attention in the future, car rental companies will inevitably develop more comprehensive and higher quality services to meet the growing needs and expectations of international travelers. provided. Car rental companies offer alternative products, so price and quality of service are key success factors. This emphasizes the importance of optimizing car rental logistics in terms of vehicle usage while maintaining high customer satisfaction, enabling the provision of a kind of "caring service".

The best way to get to your accommodation. Drivers are very polite and well behaved. They will take your package and store it safely. They make sure their customers get all the amenities and feel free while traveling. Most of them are locals so they know all the routes and directions and take their customers in the shortest distance. This saves a lot of time installing the right air conditioner, music system, car air freshener, etc.

Many people pre-book their favorite vehicle for last minute trips without any hassle. This can be achieved with the help of online sites as various agents and their services are all offered online. So you can choose the best car and get the offer you want, considering travel time, budget, etc. Most of these car rental companies are affiliated with major car companies, so you can get good quality cars for your rental purposes. People like booking because it enhances their travel experience so that they can enjoy the place, relax and have a good time with their loved ones while traveling. With increasing demand, many people are starting to offer rental cars because of the good income.

Discussion and Conclusion

As a conclusion to this essay, research has recently focused on tourists' behavioral objectives and how they relate to them. The findings of this study have significant ramifications for destination managers and researchers who are seeking to enhance domestic tourism and are thinking about how motivational factors affect satisfaction and behavioral intentions.

However, domestic travel is typically one of the tourist sectors that academics and decision-makers in developing nations give the least attention to. In order to better understand the

relationship between domestic travelers' motivations (push and pull), satisfaction, and behavioral intentions (intention to revisit and willingness to recommend), we looked at both the direct and indirect effects of motivations on behavioral intentions in this study. Create a model of domestic tourism behavior.

The data of its 15 domestic tourists from his four places in Bukhara were used to structurally evaluate this association using the Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) method of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The task had been completed. There is evidence to support the claim that both push and pull travel motivations were significant indicators of overall happiness. Additionally, it was discovered that pull travel motives directly impacted revisit intents and willingness to suggest. However, overall satisfaction had a greater influence on the likelihood of a return visit than willingness to make a referral. The link between travel motivation and return intentions was somewhat influenced by overall pleasure as well. This study also looked at push travel motivation's direct and indirect effects.

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